

Mineralogical and Chemical Assessment of Cassiterite Ore from Du, Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria as Potential Raw Materials for Tin Metal Extraction

¹Ambo, I. Amos and ²Baba, N. Mohammed and ³Idongesit, Nnammoso Akpan*

^{1&2}Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

³Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Health Sciences, Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria

(*Corresponding author: aidongesit@yahoo.com and idongesit.akpan@fuhso.edu.ng;
ORCID: ID: 0009-0009-2168-3596; <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2168-3596>

ABSTRACT

In the early 1970s, Nigeria held the 7th position on the world record for tin metal production and exportation, and that seems to be history now, as the nation's economic focus is now highly concentrated on petroleum and natural gas exploration and exportation. In Plateau State, tin mining activities date back to the early 1960s. Currently, in the Du community in Jos South of the State, huge tin ore deposits are found and locally mined by indigenes with poor derivation of economic value. Thus, the objectives of this study were to investigate the elemental, chemical/mineralogical contents and tin content of the cassiterite ore of Du in Plateau State. The study retained focus on X-ray fluorescence, Flame Atomic Absorption with inductively coupled plasma-Graphite Furnace Atomizer to examine the chemical compositions of the sample and SEM for crystal structural analysis of the ore. Results of elemental analysis showed in percentage that the ore contains: 7.168%, 6.146%, 3.471%, 2.027% of tin, zirconium, iron, and titanium, respectively and 449.29, 602.5 of Na₂O and K₂O in parts per million. The main minerals of the ore were: 60.98% SnO₂ > 8.70% SiO₂ > 5.70% ZrO₂ > 5.56% of Fe₂O₃ > 4.81% NbO > 4.07% TiO₂ > 3.26% Bi₂O₃ > 2.99 of WO₃ > 2.33% CuS₂. The results reveal that the cassiterite ores contain low silica content and a significant percentage of tin and other valuable metals and are therefore suitable raw materials for utilization for the production of cassiterite concentrates and extraction of tin metal.

Keywords: Cassiterite, Economic, Deposits, Composition, Tin, Minerals

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, in Nigeria, attention was given earlier to the agriculture and solid mineral sectors. However, with the discovery of oil minerals, the exploration of minerals such as coal, cassiterite, tantalite, etc. was abandoned due to the discovery of petroleum and natural gas. As a result of that, the development and processing of metallic ores for the extraction of valuable metals have not received adequate attention. Meanwhile, there is no doubt that, of all the naturally occurring minerals, metallic mineral ores seem to be the most abundant in the Earth's crust compared to other mineral resources such as natural gas and petroleum, which are non-renewable sources of energy (Ebbing and Gammon, 2009). In recent times, not much has been done in terms of the mineralogy of some of the metal ores, like cassiterite, which are naturally abundant in Nigeria. This makes the processing of the ores for metal extraction difficult. For cassiterite in particular, information has revealed that there are about seventy tin-bearing minerals, of which most of the minerals occur as sulfides, and the rest as oxides, hydroxides, silicates, and stannides. Nevertheless, the most important tin mineral ore is cassiterite (SnO_2), otherwise known as tin stone (Grant, 2001). Over the years, according to Idongesit *et al.* (2025), it has been recognized that cassiterite, as a tin oxide mineral, is typically found in high-temperature hydrothermal veins and granite pegmatites and greisen associated with other rock minerals such as granites, microgranites and quartz porphyries together with other oxides such as wolframite, columbite, tantalite, scheelite and hematite (Bowles, 2021). The minerals are formed through the geological movement of fluids and the slow, water-driven deposition of organic minerals over a long period of time, and the specific mineralogy and composition of tin ore deposits can vary widely depending on the geological and environmental conditions in which they are formed (Nesse, 2011).

Additionally, some of the key properties of tin ore (cassiterite), which contribute to its unique characteristics and uses for various industrial applications, particularly as a source of tin metal for various industrial applications, include: chemical composition, hardness, magnetic property, melting point, and refractive index, among others (Halдар, 2018). According to Bowles (2021), tin ore is primarily composed of tin dioxide (SnO_2), which is an oxide mineral containing tin as the main element. However, there is increasing evidence that the ore usually contains other impurities and trace elements, such as iron, manganese, tungsten, and tantalum, which can vary

depending on the specific tin ore deposit (Tapster and Bright, 2020). More so, Tapster and Bright (2020), have asserted that cassiterite (SnO_2) is the most common ore phase of tin (Sn) metal and that it typically contains $1\text{--}100 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ of uranium and relatively low concentrations of lead metal in addition to other traces of elements such as lithium, tungsten, niobium, and titanium. In addition, the literature has documented that cassiterite, as an important economic ore of tin metal, is a type of polymetallic resource mineral ore that contains metals which may include: tin, tantalum, niobium, copper, and iron (Tapster and Bright, 2020). In a recent report, Bowles (2021), it has been further established that cassiterite ore usually contains other valuable metal components to include iron, manganese, titanium, and niobium, and any of the metals can substitute for Sn with a combination of divalent and pentavalent elements replacing the tetravalent Sn, following the relationship given as shown in equation (1):

Expectedly, this substitution, according to the author, is in part responsible for the darker colored cassiterite, although it is a rather unlikely but feasible possibility.

Interestingly, the structural information about cassiterite ore has been established by Bowles (2021). The natural mineralogical form, as published by the crystal data of the structural information, suggests that the elemental atoms in cassiterite are tetragonally arranged with (space group $P4_2/mnm$), and this structure has tin atoms at the corners and center of the unit cell (Figures 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0). Again, the cell dimensions have been equally identified as $a = 4.73$ and $c = 3.18 \text{ \AA}$, with the oxygen atoms lying in the same basal plane as the tin atoms; thus making each tin atom surrounded by six oxygen atoms at the corners of an almost regular octahedron. Additionally, Bowles' report revealed certain properties of the ore with variations in terms of colour and shape as shown in Figure 2.0.

Figures 1.0, 2.0 & 3.0: Structure of Cassiterite Crystal Showing Tin and Oxygen Atoms (Adapted from Bowles (2021) and (WFI, 2023; Warr, 2021).

Furthermore, evidence for the existence of different forms of cassiterite has been reported by different researchers including Haldar (2018) and Bowles (2021). More commonly, cassiterites are often classed as gemstones, and Placer-mined tin, which is also called “stream tin” and it is important to note that these are silt-to-sand-size particles of cassiterite (Bowles, 2021). There is still considerable other evidence that cassiterite has been recognized to occur in various secondary forms in which it occurs as fine-grained or fibrous varieties with local names that describe the appearance, and where wood-tin is a common fibrous variety with concentric colloform bands resembling the growth rings of wood (Haldar, 2018), as shown in Figures (4.0-9.0).

(4.0)

(5.0)

(6.0)

(7.0)

(8.0)

(9.0)

Figures 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0, & 9.0: 4.0 & 5.0 are Faceted Crystal of Cassiterite Ore: Adapted from (Adam, 1998); 6.0 & 7.0 Are Crystal of Cassiterite Adapted from (King, 2022); 8.0 & 9.0 are Wood tin cassiterite, from Durango Mexico and is Cassiterite Crystals, Blue Tier Tin-Field, from Tasmania, Australia Respectively Adapted from (WFI, 2023).

With the rising cost of living, building and construction, educational materials, electricity, and health care facilities, it is noteworthy that many nations of the world have diversified their economy with a focus now on metallic ore (Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, Henckens (2021) reported that cassiterite mining and tin production tripled in the 20th century, but in contrast to many other raw materials, tin production growth was linear rather than exponential; the world tin production in 2019 was 310,000 tons and a little above that value in 2020 (Figure 10.0).

Figure 10.0: Main Tin Producing Countries of the World: US Geological Survey (USGS, 2020)

In Nigeria, tin ore is mined in Plateau State, with large deposits of the ore being found in Du community in Jos South Local Government Area of the state. The metal was produced in large quantities in the early seventies, before about 1957, when Nigeria provided 4 % of the world's

tin and was the 7th largest producer of tin in the world (Ogwuegbu *et al.*, 2011; Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). However, the nation’s economic attention has shifted, with focus now on crude oil and natural gas, presumably because it has proven to be more successful in terms of revenue accrued to the Nigerian government. Unfortunately, there have been a number of attempts in the past to develop other mineral sectors in Nigeria, particularly the solid mineral sector, but such efforts have not yielded the expected growth of the sector. At the moment, it has become increasingly worrisome that Nigeria which reported of becoming a rapidly growing source of tin-in-concentrate in 2017, with tin ore exported in the first four months of the year at totals of importing country’s data at 2,967 tons (gross weight) or an estimated 2,000 tons of tin contained based on a 67 % average tin content with the reported growth as shown in Figure 11.0 (NGSA, 2017), is now grabbing with unclear shipments quantity.

Figure 11.0: Chart of Nigerian Tin Metal Exports Between 2014 and 2017: (NGSA, 2017)

Therefore, the current status of Nigeria in tin production is lamentable, and the situation has continued to necessitate ongoing research and innovation, which are expected to be supported by the government's political will. To navigate the complex mineral processing situations through the application of emerging modern scientific and technological approaches requires several steps, and thus, there is an urgent need for government at all levels to rise to the occasion by utilizing available scientific research information for adequate and effective utilization of Nigeria’s solid minerals sector to explore minerals like tin for national economic benefits. Meanwhile, globally, considerable interest in tin ore has continued to grow, with the focus being on the application of modern techniques for tin ore deposits assessment, mining, and tin metal extraction. Nevertheless, it is necessary to understand that humans have extracted tin from

cassiterite ores for thousands of years, since it is relatively simple to refine, as tin was one of the first metals that humans learned to use during the Bronze Age (Hong, 2015; Fosu *et al.*, 2024).

Tin metal and tin-related processed products like tin cans (Cumhur, 2012), have found several applications, with many examples of tin products such as solder, tin plating alloy wire, tin chemicals, brass and bronze, specialized alloys, PVC stabilizers, and Li-ion batteries being used in our everyday life. Additionally, Süli (2019) and Warr ((2021) indicated that tin is essential for producing solder on PCBs and in packaging applications, and many other uses, such as in the manufacture of biocides and fungicides. With the extensive applications of tin metal, cassiterite ore is essential and beneficial to human life and a reliable source of minerals for industrial advancement (Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, it is not probable to assert that cassiterite ore mining and processing have been conducted for thousands of years, with tin metal continuing to play a very significant role in human history, particularly in the production of bronze and in copper alloys (Fosu *et al.*, 2024; Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). In addition to these, it was widely used in ancient civilizations for tools, weapons, and in artwork (Klein and Philpotts, 2013; Hong, 2015; Fosu *et al.*, 2024). It is important to note that the tin market is undoubtedly driven by global demand, supply and production trends, and various applications across industries (Idongesit *et al.*, 2025).

However, despite its usefulness, cassiterite ore has continued to receive little attention regardless of its common occurrence and economic importance and surprisingly, the mineralogical information on cassiterite ores is generally scarce and in Nigeria in particular where tin mining activities have been known to have existed in Plateau state for over two decades, there is almost no available substantial information on cassiterite ores mined in the state (Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). Except, it is striking that most of the studies conducted in that area are on tailings for the extraction of other metals like iron and copper. Again, although commercially important quantities of cassiterite occur in placer deposits in tailings, however, there is also considerable other evidence that cassiterite also occurs in granite and pegmatite-associated deposits (Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). Meanwhile, Abubakre and co-workers have reported on exploring the potential of tailings of Bukuru Jos South cassiterite Deposit in Plateau State, Nigeria for the Production of Iron ore Pellets (Abubakre *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, in another classic study, Ogwuegbu and co-workers have reported on the mineralogical characterization of Kuru cassiterite ore in Plateau

State by SEM-EDS, XRD, and ICP Techniques (Ogwuegbu *et al.*, 2011). Other available reports on tin mining activities in Jos, Plateau include that of Cooper (2021), and that of Nigerian Geological Survey Agency (NGSA) records volume 14, under the Ministry of Mines and Steel Development (NGSA, 2017). Very recently, Idongesit *et al.* (2025) have reported the study of the eco-friendly chemical leaching of cassiterite ore obtained from Du, Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria, in acidic media for tin extraction.

Essentially, as the global demand for tin metal has received attention quite out of proportion to its general importance, there is considerable interest in other sources of tin metal for the possible extraction of tin. In that regard, Bunnakkha and Jarupisitthorn (2012), reported the extraction of tin from Hardhead by oxidation and fusion with sodium hydroxide, and equally recently, Yuma *et al.* (2020), have reported hydrometallurgical extraction of tin from cassiterite ore in Kalima (DR Congo) by alkaline fusion with a eutectic mixture of alkali hydroxides (sodium and potassium). More recently, it has been recognized that it might become a serious issue for original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) to meet up the annual high rising demand for tin for production of wires, in the coating of electronic enclosures and housings (Süli, 2019; Idongesit *et al.*, 2025), and the idea still persists in some quarters, perhaps because little efforts have been directed to cassiterite ores analysis and provision of mineralogical information for reasonable extraction of tin metal. Interestingly too, as this view is still persisting for some time, it has caused many other researchers to spring up in an attempt, like this very particular study, to provide useful information that would guide, in general, the extraction of tin metal from cassiterite ores.

Meanwhile, it should however, be mentioned that the desirability of human to effectively exploit mineral resources like cassiterite ores and maximize their full economic benefits could be accomplished through the use of modern technologies based on available information about such minerals. Therefore, it is pertinent to note that the identification and characterization of mineral compositions of mineral ores is of fundamental importance in the development of technologies and operations of mining and mineral processing systems (Khairulnizan, 2022), and it is equally very important in choosing suitable technologies and flowsheet that are less cost, eco-friendly and minimize greenhouse gases emission for the recovering of the constituent metals (Idongesit

et al., 2025). Additionally, and more importantly, it is also critical in optimizing the actual technological conditions of either pyrometallurgical plant or hydrometallurgical methodologies for improving both operational performance and expected outputs (Khairulnizan, 2022; Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). According to Khairulnizan (2022) and Idongesit *et al.* (2025), the growing need for detailed information about the mineralogical composition of a mineral deposit therefore determines that mineral characterization studies form an integral and often critical part of investigations of mineral ore deposits.

Interestingly, it is imperative to further establish that it has been well recognized that the knowledge of mineralogical or chemical composition, ores' particle sizes, morphology and elemental association with other minerals in mineral ores like cassiterite is therefore expected to provide insights and information on the characteristics, type, nature and amount of minerals and elements present within the ore at different locations that would permit an assessment and determination of the optimal processing route for its constituent minerals/metals extraction (Khairulnizan, 2022; Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). In addition, various researchers have evaluated different mineral ores and have provided evidence that a rather unlikely but feasible possibility of mineral ore deposits located even in a particular geographical location do not have the same mineralogical and elemental compositions due to different processes of formation, soil mineral compositions and conditions, and different geological locations and disposition (Anthony *et al.*, 2005; Idongesit *et al.*, 2025). Based on the foregoing, although it is true that all mineral ore deposits at a particular location in a community or state or country or continent may have different mineralogical compositions, it is also true that the different mineralogical compositions can be ascertained through proper experimental mineralogical assessment like this kind of ours. It can be argued that more commonly, the preceding observations are often used as the rationale to assess mineral ores so as to decide and establish the gainfulness of such ores using modern technologies for a specific deposit to ascertain the various applications and value chain addition.

Clearly, it is somewhat ironic that despite the abundant deposits of cassiterite ores in Du, Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria, and increased global interest in the cassiterite ores and with the global high demand for tin metal in the telecommunication industry for soldering work (Idongesit *et al.*, 2025), cassiterite mineralogical assessment has received very little attention. In fact, at the moment, there is a drought of information on the mineralogical/chemical and

elemental composition of cassiterite ore deposits in the Du community in Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria. Therefore, with the global increasingly scarce supplies of cassiterite concentrates and tin metal, there is an urgent and growing need for cassiterite ore deposits to be adequately assessed in terms of their mineralogical and chemical compositions in order to ascertain their suitability for the preparation of cassiterite concentrates and the extraction of tin metal.

Given the above, this study is aimed at not only assessing the mineralogy of the cassiterite ore but also its elemental composition for possible processing into concentrates and tin and other metals for value chain addition that would enhance economic, industrial, and technological advancement of Nigerian society in particular and the African continent in general. In general, the purpose of this study is to gain some understanding of the mineralogical composition of the cassiterite ore for the extraction of tin metal, and it is reasonable to expect that this study, as vital as it is, has obtained accurate mineralogical, physico-chemical properties, elemental compositions, and the percentage tin content of the cassiterite ore mined from Du. The mineralogical composition and elemental characteristics of Du Cassiterite ore deposit were performed by a combination of different instrumental methodologies, including X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Inductively Coupled Plasma-Graphite Furnace Atomizer and flame Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) to examine the chemical compositions of the samples and SEM for crystal structural analysis. The rationale and the general impression are that it would be of great value if the results of this study would be carefully used over the coming years and we equally believe that these results will become increasingly widespread for a variety of mineralogical studies to add a further tool to the arsenal of parameters and information available for mineralogical study of cassiterite ores in particular and other mineral ores in general.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study area is located at Du, a local village in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State of Nigeria. There are ongoing mining activities for tin in the area, with active mining sites where cassiterite ore (SnO_2), used for this work, was collected. Geographically, Du in Jos South of Plateau State (9.8965° N, 8.8583° E) is in the North central zone of Nigeria, and the occupations of the local community are predominantly subsistence farming, hunting, and local

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mining. The tribal dwellers of Du community in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State are typical the Berom tribe who are mainly peasant farmers and while Figure 12.0 is the map of Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State showing Du, Figures 13a 13b, 13c, 13d, 13e and 13f show the plates of snapped images of mining sites in the area and Figure 14.0 shows the plates of snapped images the cassiterite ores.

Figure 12.0: Map of Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State, Showing Du (adapted from Research Gate).

Figures 13a, 13b, 13c, 13d, 13e & 13f: Plates of Snapped Images of Cassiterite Ore Mining Sites at Du, Jos South, Plateau State, Nigeria, Showing Miners on Mining Activities.

Figure 14.0: Plates of Images of Cassiterite Ores Mined from Du, Jos South, Plateau State

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Sample Collection

Up to 5.0 kg of the crude cassiterite ore was purchased from the local miners who are also the indigen of the community at five different active mining sites located at a distance apart. The samples were collected in sterilized polyethylene bags and were transported to the laboratory prior to analysis.

Sample Preparation

Crushing and Grinding

1.0 kg cassiterite tin ore (SnO_2) was crushed into 1-inch size using a laboratory jaw crusher (10-300TPH concrete crusher, China), and then followed by homogenization and sieving, and then divided into two equal portions. One portion was further crushed to less than (-2 mm) particles using jaw and roller crushers (2PG series, 350 x 350Jpeq, Japan). The samples were then riffled to obtain a representative sample by using a Jones Riffler according to the descriptions in Idongesit *et al.* (2025) and Soltani *et al.* (2021). The representative sample was, in addition, milled into a powder form by using a laboratory ball mill, and the well-prepared powder form of the sample was ready for mineralogical analysis and leaching experiments.

Analysis

SEM and XRF Analysis

A portion of the powdered ore samples (20.0 g) was analyzed for structural arrangement of particles in the ore using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and for optical mineralogical properties. For the XRF analysis, fine powder ore samples were mixed with a binding aid and pressed to produce homogeneous sample pellets, and thereafter the samples were subjected to XRF analysis (Soltani *et al.*, 2021).

Thermochemical Tests

Thermal tests were performed by heating 25.0 g of the cassiterite ore powder mixed with fine crystals of K_2SO_4 in the ratio of 2:3 to high temperatures (2000 °C) using a muffle electric

furnace (SX-5-12; PC:22070222/2000 °C), and the melting behavior of the ore was carefully observed within four hours.

Density Measurement

This measurement was performed using a density balance and also with a relative density glass bottle (50 ml/20 °C) in order to determine the density of the ore, and this has provided additional information for the characterization of the ore. Additionally, Archimedes' principal method was further utilized to confirm the density of the ore using this relationship.

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Mass of a substance}}{\text{Volume of the substance}} = \frac{\text{Mass of the complex}}{\text{Change in volume}}$$

Magnetism Test

Magnetism property tests of the cassiterite ore were performed using a bar magnet and were further confirmed using a magnetic separator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.0: Result of Physico-Chemical Properties of Cassiterite Ore

Property	Result
Colour	Greyish black
Hardness	6.72
Thermal property (Melting Point)	1698 °C/3,088 °F/1971 K
Density	6.52
Specific Gravity	6.52
Loss of Ignition (LOI)	2200
Magnetic Property	Non-magnetic
Lustre	High metallic lustre

The results of the physico-chemical properties of the ore (Table 1.0) show that the ore is heavily dense which is in agreement with the reports of many other researchers in the literature who have reported that cassiterite ore has a density within the range of 6.4 to 7.1 g/cm³. Additionally, the tin ore has a high thermal property (melting temperature) of 1698 °C/3,088 °F/1971 K which is in agreement with the report by Henckens (2021), (1720 °C). The result of the magnetic property suggests that the ore possesses non-magnetic behavior with dense and black-grayish in appearance in colour.

The result of the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the ore and the weight loss observed under the temperature range between 210 °C and 250 °C. It is believed that it may be due to the loss of physically absorbed water or the evaporation of adsorbed water from the surface of the ore particles. The weight loss was also observed between 1175 °C and 1250 °C is believed to be mainly due to the decomposition of the K₂SO₄ as the salt decomposes at temperatures above 1150 °C (Wang *et al.*, 2019). The weight loss observed under the temperature range between 1600 °C and 1650 °C may be due to the decomposition of the ore and the steady weight loss under the temperature ranges between 1650 °C and 1698 °C with an endothermic curve noticed within the temperatures as shown in (Figure 15.0)

Figure 15.0: Thermochemical Behaviour of Cassiterite Ore

Table 2.0: Result of Crystal Properties of Cassiterite Ore

Property	Result
Unit Cell	$a = 4.7384(4)\text{\AA}$, $c = 3.1872(1)\text{\AA}$; $Z = 2.0$
Space group	$P4_2/mnm$
Refractive Index	$n_o = 2.00$; $n_e = 2.095$
Dispersion	0.069
Crystal System	Tetragonal
Crystal Class	Tetragonal dipyramidal ($4/mmm$); ($4/m\ 2/m\ 2/m$)

The crystallographic information of the ore shown in Table 2.0 indicates the general impression that the ore crystal system is tetragonal with cubic crystal sides ($a(\text{\AA})/c(\text{\AA})$) (in Armstrong unit) as $a = 4.7384(4)\text{\AA}$, $c = 3.1872(1)\text{\AA}$. Interestingly, also, a noteworthy feature of the data in (Table 2.0) is the space group ($P4_2/mnm$) and the contribution number to one cell ($Z = 2$), which further confirms the crystal information.

Table 3.0: Result of Mineralogical Composition of the Cassiterite Ore

Mineral	Composition in (ppm)	% Composition
SiO ₂	87000	8.70
Fe ₂ O ₃	55600	5.56
SnO ₂	609800	60.98
ZrO ₂	57000	5.70
WO ₃	2986	2.99
NbO	48110	4.81
TiO ₂	40675	4.07
Bi ₂ O ₃	32628.2	3.26
CuS ₂	23250	2.33
MnO ₂	6939	0.694
SeO ₂	649	0.065
K ₂ O	602.50	0.0603

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Na ₂ O	449.29	0.0449
As ₂ O ₃	629	0.063
Al ₂ O ₃	6500	0.65
Co ₃ O ₄	33	0.0033
Cr ₂ O ₃	17	0.0017
VO ₂	11	0.0011
SrO	5.4	0.00054
LOI	2200	0.22

The result of the mineralogical composition of the ore presented in Table 3.0 shows that the ore is rich in tin oxide content amounting to 60.98 % of the oxide. As shown in (Table 3.0), the ore is low in silica content of about 8.70 %. The low silica content will lead to low consumption of processing chemicals and will enhance the availability of the metals for processing. From the mineralogical standpoint, the total percentage of minerals detected is 100 %, including loss of ignition (LOI) at (> 1000 °C), and the total percentage of minerals identified with a significant amount in the ore is 99.05 %. The traditional explanation for this is that those are the principal minerals of the ore. The ore is made up of two major types of minerals, oxides and sulphides. The oxide minerals are more abundant due to the mineralization process and the available Earth's minerals, and the geological location. The minerals identified in their order of abundance are: SiO₂ > ZrO₂ > Fe₂O₃ > NbO > TiO₂ > Bi₂O₃ > WO₃ > CuS₂. From the result, the ore has a significant percentage of tin metal oxide which can be economically exploited for the extraction of an appreciable percentage of tin metal. Contrary to the unequivocal assertion that only stanniferous pegmatites cassiterite ore formed in the areas where mineralization is associated with deep-seated intrusions of acid granites are the type of cassiterite ores mined in the Republic of Congo, and Nigeria (Khairulnizan, 2022), it is equally worthwhile to become aware of the occurrence of Placer-mined tin which is also called “stream tin” in Du, Plateau State, Nigeria and it is important also to note that these are silt-to-sand-size particles of cassiterite ores (Bowles, 2021) as shown in Figures 14.0.

Table 4.0: Result of Elemental Composition of the Cassiterite Ore

Element	Percentage Composition
Sb	0.00
Sn	7.168
Cd	0.00
Pd	0.00
Ag	0.022
Bal	75.194
Mo	0.00
Nb	2.976
Zr	6.146
Sr	0.003
Rb	0.00
Bi	0.542
As	0.053
Se	0.187
Au	0.00
Pt	0.00
Pb	0.00
W	1.176
Zn	0.00
Cu	0.665
Ni	0.00
Co	0.032
Fe	3.471
Mn	0.257
Cr	0.015
V	0.010
Ti	2.027
Ca	0.00
K	0.055

The result in Table 4.0 shows the XRF elemental composition of the ore. The ore contains 7.168 % of free tin metal, 6.146 % of zirconium metal, 3.471 % of iron and 2.976 % of niobium. Other metals with significant percentage abundance include titanium (2.027 %), tungsten (1.176 %). Fundamentally, the ore has a high abundance of boron aluminide (Bal) mineral (75.194 %). The elements identified in their order of concentrations are Bal > Sn > Zr > Fe > Nb > Ti > W > Cu > Bi > Mn > Se (Table 5). The ore contained some other elements that include: K (0.055), As (0.053), Co (0.032), Ag (0.022), Cr (0.015), V (0.010), Sr (0.003). From the results obtained,

however, boron aluminide (Bal) is found naturally in the ore and the alloyed substance is of interest because of its usefulness and application in aerospace. As shown in Table 4.0, the cassiterite ore has tin, zirconium and iron in significant concentrations for consideration in terms of processing for application. The presence of a high percentage of boron aluminide (Bal) in the ores, as shown in Figure 16.0, suggests that the cassiterite ore from Du in Plateau State, Nigeria, is strategic for exploitation for prospective applications in both energy and aerospace industries, in addition to the solid mineral industry. Meanwhile, although it is unclear what forms the alloy in association with the ores and with our meager information in that regard, we will suggest that further studies be carried out on the cassiterite ores.

Figure 16.0: A Chart of Percentage Elemental Composition of the Cassiterite Ore

Result of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The result of the scanning electron microscope is presented in Figure 17.0. The image shows the distribution of the minerals in the ore which are finely distributed in the ore as shown in the image. This will be used to evaluate the extent of leaching of the ore. Additionally, the SEM result in (Figure 17.0) shows the image of cassiterite ore as the arrangement of fine particles within the ore crystallographic structure. The cassiterite mineral is irregularly spread through the

pegmatite body as large black or dark brown dipyramidal crystals, which agrees with the assertion made in Khairulnizan (2022).

Figure 17.0: Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) of Cassiterite Ore Obtained by Thermo Fisher Scientific Machine, 2 Radcliff Road, Tewksbury, Ma 01876, USA; XL3-98293.

CONCLUSION

The cardinal focus of this study was to use various instrumental methodologies to analyze cassiterite ore mined from Du in Jos South, Plateau, Nigeria to characterize the ore in terms of its mineralogical and elemental compositions and to ascertain whether the ores are rich in tin and other metals for possible commercial industrial extraction. Certainly, the recognition of the existence of Placer cassiterite ores in Du deposits is not surprising as such has been mentioned in the literature as being in Jos, Plateau State. Meanwhile, the general impression of the results of the mineralogical composition of the cassiterite ore is that the ore is rich in tin oxide (SnO_2) to the tune of 60.98 %, followed by silica (8.70 %), zircon dioxide (5.70 % of ZrO_2), hematite (5.56 % of Fe_2O_3), niobium oxide (4.81 % of NbO) and titania (4.07 % of TiO_2). A noteworthy feature of cassiterite ore, as indicated by mineralogical data, is that the ore is approximately 97.61% rich in oxide minerals, while the remaining 2.39% is comprised of sulphide minerals. Another exciting conclusion drawn about the ore is that its tin metal content of 7.168 % is moderately good and adequate for large-scale or commercial extraction. Again, it is also crystal clear and reasonable to agree that the ore is moderately good in content of other metals, such as 6.146 % of

Zr, 3.471 % of Fe, 2.976 % of Nb and 2.027 % of Ti. Additionally, we the investigators, have argued that the discovery of the existence of naturally occurring boron aluminide (Bal) in the ore which has not been reported elsewhere in the literature, has made this work novel.

At this point, it is worthwhile, after all, to believe that the above detailed explanations suggest that the assessment of the inherent mineralogical composition of the cassiterite ores mined from Du community in Jos South of Plateau State, Nigeria, reveals that the ores contain low silica content and significant percentage of tin metal and other valuable metals and are therefore suitable raw materials for utilization for production of cassiterite concentrates and extraction of tin metal. We therefore call on the governments of Nigeria at all levels (Idongesit *et al.*, 2025b) (Local government, Plateau State government and the Federal Ministry of Solid Minerals), private industries, foreign investors and individual manufacturers to avail themselves with this information to explore the possible maximum exploitation of the natural abundance mineral resources of the area for economic benefit of Plateau State and Nigeria in particular and African continent in general.

SUGGESTION

We would like to suggest that further studies be carried out on the cassiterite ore deposits at Du in Jos, South Plateau State, Nigeria, particularly for the extraction of boron aluminide (Bal) that is found to be naturally occurring in a large percentage of 75.194 % of the ores.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Professor Ambo, I. Amos, conceptualized and composed the topic, supervised the research work, and read-proof the paper's manuscript. Professor Baba, N. Mohammed, co-supervised the work and the drafting of the paper's manuscript, while Idongesit Nnammonso Akpan performed the tasks of carrying out the research work, drafting the manuscript, typesetting, editing, and proper referencing, as well as the production of the final draft of the paper's manuscript.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data backing up the findings of this investigation will be made readily accessible by the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

CONSENT AND ETHICAL APPROVAL

Since all the sources of information used in this investigation, which are in the public domain, have been duly acknowledged, and additional ethical approval and consent were obtained while taking the snapped shots pictures of the local miners, therefore, there was no ethical violation in this work.

DECLARATIONS OF CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors of this paper declare that they have no known existed competing interest during and after the production of the paper.

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